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COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH A MICROSTRUCTURE WHICH GIVES THE POSSIBILITY INCREASING SERVICE PROPERTIES DURING EXPLOITATION

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SUMMARY: We have studied a microstructure of composites' matrix based on polymers and soluble silicates with increasing chemical resistance and decreasing permeability. For polymeric materials the most effective is a simultaneous lowering of permeability and increase in chemical resistance through the addition of inorganic substances selectively interacting with water or an aggressive medium with the formation of system of high-strength hydrate complexes – inorganic adhesive cements. When a polymer the chemical degradation of which takes place in the diffusional –kinetic region is used the matrix of a composite material, additives forming with diffusing liquid medium a system consisting of a high – strength and water-stable inorganic cement, which is also fulfilling micro cracks, pores and other defects, not only permit a decrease by 1.5-2 orders of magnitude in permeability but also, in number of cases, lead to an increase in the strength of the composite material during use. The experimental data will present for more than 20 composite materials based on thermoplastic and rubber matrixes. Formation into polymer composite materials new crystal-hydrate complexes was determinate by methods of electron-microscope investigation and X-ray structural analysis.

KEYWORDS: Composite Materials, Polymer Matrix, Silicate Matrix, Chemical Resistance, Permeability.

INTRODUCTION

Coatings and linings based on chemically resistant polymers and silicate corrosion-resistant materials are widely used for the protection of metals from corrosion in aggressive media.(1)

In the general case, the service life of a coating, τ is made up of the following components:

$$\tau = \tau_d + \tau_a + \tau_e + \tau_c$$

(1)

where:

τ_d - is the time for the diffusion front of the components of the medium to reach the surface of the metal;

τ_a - is the time of the fall in the strength of the adhesive linkage between the coating and the metal, including the Induction period of corrosion,

τ_e - is the time to reach the critical level of corrosion losses or the local destruction of the coating by corrosion products from the beginning of the contact of the metal with the medium as a phase;

τ_c is the time to reach the critical level of corrosion losses at the bottom of a pore or a fissure.

An increase in τ at each stage gives an increase in the protective properties as a whole.

For polymeric materials the effective is a simultaneous lowering of permeability and increase in chemical resistance through the addition of inorganic substances selectively interacting with water or an aggressive medium with the formation of a system of high-strength hydrate complexes - inorganic adhesive cements. Such additives are, in the main, metal oxides - the pulverulent part of acid- or alkali-hardening adhesive cements. When a polymer the chemical degradation of which takes place in the diffusional-kinetic region is used as the matrix of a composite material, additives forming with the diffusing liquid medium a system consisting of a high-strength and water-impermeable inorganic cement not only permit a decrease by 1.5-2 orders of magnitude in permeability but also in a number of cases, lead to an increase in the strength of the material during use [2].

The effectiveness of such type of additives is concerned with following transformation into modified polymer materials:

- while interacting additives with aggressive media crystal hydrates are forming into micropores, microracks and others; as a result such microdefects are 'healed up', filling up a new high-straight cementing phase, and a material is strengthening;
- while forming crystal hydrates a volume and a specific surface of contacts zones of such additives are decreasing into a practically constant volume of a polymer matrix; as a result compressing stresses are appearing, thickening a material's structure and decreasing its uncombined volume; by the expense of increasing of the material's specific surface by forming the new phase with binding properties an adhesion at the boundary line between the polymer and this active filler;
- into the top layers of a materials the penetrated aggressive medium is spending for new phase forming, decreasing a rate of medium's penetration and following sorption for subsequent layers.

The diffusion of acids in hydrophobous thermoplastics is characterized by the strike front of diffusion, the displacement of which with time is described by the equation (3):

$$(2) \quad X := \lambda \sqrt{\tau}$$

where :

X - the deepness of the penetration of the acid into the polymer during the time duration τ ;

λ - "the penetration constant" determined by the nature of the polymer, the nature and the concentration of the acid in the exterior medium, and by the temperature.

The methods of estimation of the deepness of the penetration of acids into the filled polymers have been the same that those for studies of the acid diffusion into non-filled polymers – indicator and trace methods. Involving additives does not change the tendencies of the diffusional process for most of the cases. This one is characterized by the value of "penetration constant" with value shorter than for its analogue in the non-filled polymer λ_0 . In some cases, the slow motion of the diffusion front has appeared. One observed even stopping of the diffusion front.

According to the aim of the experiments, the additive concentrations have been presented in grams or mole per unit of the mass or the volume. Additives have been involved into

polyolephins and fluoride plastics. The diffusion of HCl, HF and HNO₃ from solutions of various concentrations into the polymers was studied.

The effectiveness of additives can be characterized by the parameter γ showing how many times the acid appear at the exit from the filled polymer; τ_{of} is larger than this one for the non-filled polymer τ_0 :

$$\gamma := \frac{\tau_{of}}{\tau_0}$$

(3)

For thickness coating the equation is the following:

$$\gamma := \left\{ \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_f} \right\}^2 \quad (4)$$

The influence of the nature of the polymer on the parameter β characterizing the diffusion is not simple but depends on the kind of the acid (see Table 1).

Table 1. Additive effectiveness β (kg/mole), for various additives of the diffusion of HCl into polymers (* - sodium bicarbonate; ** - (CuOH)₂CO₃).

Additive Element	Oxide		Hydride			Carbonate	
	Valence						
	II	III	I	II	III	I	II
Li			29				
Be	29-14						
Na			63			11;3*	
Mg	24-14					16	
Al		24			5		
K			86				
Ca	20-14						29-24
Mn							24
Co	16						
Cu	2.5			16			7**
Zn	8						
Sr							29-24
Cd	47						

Ba	8			2			47
Bi		7					

The data of Table 1 show that for HCl and HF the value of β decreases in the range of polymers. Theoretical considerations allow assumption that the influence of the nature of the polymer on the efficiency of the inhibition that is related to its sorptive capacity against the acid: the more the sorption is constant, striker the inhibition effects. The data about the constants of sorption of acids by polymers are very poor, therefore it is impossible to correctly check this assumption. The mass change of the non-filled polymer after the 24-hours in aq. HCl medium is just compared to the value of γ . These results are presented on Fig. 1 along twice-logarithm coordinates. At low degrees of filling, γ increases linearly with the additive concentration ϕ .

Fig. 1. Correlation between the value of γ and the change of the polymer mass (% of the initial) after exposition in HCl: 1 - penton; 2 - F-2M; 3 - F-40; 4 - PELP; 5 - F-30.

When a polymer the chemical degradation of which takes place in the diffusional kinetic region is used as the matrix of a composite material, additives forming with the diffusing liquid medium a system consisting of high-strength and water-impermeable inorganic cement not only permit a decrease by 1.5-2 orders of magnitude in permeability but also, in a number of cases, lead to an increase in the strength of the material at use. For example, for an epoxide-rubber mastic the introduction of the complex additive $n\text{TiO}_2 \times m\text{CuO} \times p\text{CdCO}_3$ leads to an increase in the strength indices on prolonged exposure in 85% orthophosphoric acid by a factor of 1.5-1.6. Without the additive the material is destroyed during the first month of exposure in this medium.

It has been shown that various disperse systems suitable for adding to composite polymeric materials exist that give high-strength cements with sulfuric, nitric, and hydrofluoric acids and with potassium hydroxide (see, as example, fig 2,3). An increase in longevity of a glass reinforced polyester plastic in sodium hydroxide and of a glass-reinforced epoxide plastic in sulfuric acid on the introduction of an active additive into the gelcoat layer has also been

shown. A similar effect has also been obtained for highly filled polyester composites used in acid and alkaline media.

Fig. 2 Correlation between the tensile strength of liquid ebonite covering materials and the time of exposure (10% HNO₃, 293K): 1 - without additives; 2 - with additive, based on oxide of bismuth.

Fig. 3 Correlation between the compressive strength of epoxy-phenolic composite materials and the time of exposure (30% sulfuric acid, 293K): 1 - without additives; 2 - with additive, based on copper oxide.

We have elaborated now more than 150 additives for different polymer matrix working in different aggressive media. Particularly effective in composite materials based on soluble silicates, mainly quarternary ammonia soluble silicates, is the addition of tetrafururyloxyane, since the silica in molecular form formed in the technological stage on its partial hydrolytic oligomerization is a center of microcrystallization of the silicate phase which permits not only a decrease in the permeability of the coating by 23 orders of magnitude but also a 1.5-to 2-fold rise in its strength. More complex data of this investigation was present early in (4).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the theory of “positive corrosion” for nonmetallic materials, the advanced method increasing protective properties of polymer materials has been proposed. The method implies adding of powdery inorganic active fillers interacting into polymer matrix with penetrated aggressive media. The mechanism of formation of new phases as a result of such interacting was observed. A lot of elaborated additives were successfully tested for many kinds of polymer protective materials and different types of matrix polymers. Elaborated materials have shown significant increasing protective properties.

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